

Recommended citation: Radmehr, F., Nedaei, M., & Rezvanifard, F. (2021). Task design in engineering mathematical courses: The case of problem-posing and puzzle tasks. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1192-1200). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650418.

TASK DESIGN IN ENGINEERING MATHEMATICAL COURSES: THE CASE OF PROBLEM POSING AND PUZZLE TASKS

F. Radmehr¹

Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway; Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway; Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad, Iran
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0592-9148>

M. Nedaei

Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad, Iran; University of Agder, Kristiansand, Norway
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8196-6736>

F. Rezvanifard

Ferdowsi University of Mashhad
Mashhad, Iran
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4433-2982>

Conference Key Areas: *Mathematics, Attractiveness.*

Keywords: *Mathematics, task design, problem posing, puzzle tasks.*

ABSTRACT

Several studies have reported that engineering mathematical courses are not appealing to some engineering students, and they found these courses dry and boring. This paper shares our experience of using problem-posing and puzzle tasks in two mathematical engineering courses, differential equations and calculus. In the first study, 135 first-year undergraduate engineering students from a public university in Iran engaged with eight problem-posing tasks related to integral calculus. In the second study, 135 undergraduate engineering students from the same university engaged in solving four puzzle tasks related to the first-order differential equations in self-selected groups of two or three students. Students' attitudes towards engaging in these two types of tasks were explored using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The findings indicate that more than 50 percent of engineering students had positive attitudes towards using mathematical problem-posing tasks in engineering mathematical courses. Regarding using puzzle tasks, the findings indicate that more than 50 percent of students were unanimous puzzle tasks are entertaining and enjoyable activities and perceived that solving puzzle tasks could improve students' problem-solving skills, modelling, and thinking skills in engineering differential equations courses. The findings of these two studies suggest that

¹ *Corresponding Author*

F. Radmehr

f.radmehr65@gmail.com; farzad.radmehr@ntnu.no

problem-posing and puzzle tasks could be used more often in engineering mathematical courses to motivate students to learn mathematics.

1 INTRODUCTION

Engineering mathematical courses are not appealing to some engineering students, and they found these courses dry and boring [1-2]. As tertiary mathematics educators, we need to think about what type of tasks could make the teaching of mathematics at the tertiary level for engineering students more appealing and at the same time engage them in inquiry into mathematics and activate higher-order thinking. In the 21st century, simply remembering and applying mathematical knowledge in familiar situations is not enough, and students need to engage in activities that prepared them for solving real-world problems [3]. In this paper, we share our experience of two types of tasks, problem-posing and puzzle tasks, that we speculate engineering students would enjoy engaging with them and finding them interesting. Additionally, these two types of tasks were highlighted as tasks which can activate higher-order thinking in the students' mind [3-4]. In the following, we define problem posing and puzzle tasks and describe the relevant literature about them before presenting the research question.

2 LITERATURE

2.1 Problem-posing tasks

A problem posing activity in mathematics is “the process of formulating and expressing a problem within the domain of mathematics” [5, p. 2]. Problem posing can play an important role in mathematical teaching and learning [5]. Mathematical problem-posing activities have been found beneficial for both pupils and teachers in school mathematics. Previous studies have suggested that engaging with problem-posing tasks could help students to develop their conceptual understanding of mathematics [5], develop their critical thinking skills [6], problem-solving skills [5], and positively impact their attitudes towards mathematics [7]. It can also help teachers better understand students' mathematical thinking [5].

Several frameworks have been proposed for designing problem-posing tasks [7-8], and how students posed problems can be evaluated [7, 9]. In terms of designing problem-posing tasks, students could be given pictures, diagrams, equations, a solution, or a short story, and then they will be asked to pose problem(s) with this piece of information [3, 8]. In terms of evaluating posed problems, several dimensions have been considered in the previous studies [7, 9]. For instance, we could investigate whether the posed problem is solvable based on the given information, or we could analyse the context of the posed problem whether it is situated in a bare mathematics context, or the posed problem is realistic or authentic [9].

2.2 Puzzle tasks

A task is called a puzzle if it has most of the four following criteria: *Generality* (help us to learn some of the general mathematical problem-solving principles), *simplicity* (easy to state and remember), *entertaining* (presented in an entertaining way), and after solving it we experience the *Eureka* moment [2]. Additionally, three types of puzzle tasks have been identified in the previous literature: *Sophism*, *paradox*, and *puzzle* [1]. A sophism can be defined as an “intentionally invalid reasoning that looks formally correct, but in fact contains a subtle mistake or flaw” [1, p.1106]. A paradox is a “surprising, unexpected, counter-intuitive statement that looks invalid but in fact is true” [1, p.1106]. Students, when engaging with sophisms and paradoxes, analyse the given tasks and evaluate reasoning(s) included in them, which often help them to have a deeper understanding of the concept(s) included in the tasks [3]. The third type is called puzzle, which is a “non-standard, non-routine, unstructured” [1, p. 1106] task presented in an entertaining way, and they are similar to modelling mathematics tasks.

Puzzle-based learning (PzBL) refers to engaging students with puzzle tasks to enhance students’ problem solving and thinking skills [2]. Previous studies have suggested that PzBL could improve students’ motivation in learning mathematics and help students solve real-world problems [10]. Students engaging in puzzle problems could learn various problem-solving strategies that could be used to solve problems in their future careers [2, 10].

Higher-order thinking can be activated by engaging students with puzzle tasks, as students are required to analyse and check all the reasoning used in sophism and paradox tasks to verify or refute them [3]. Also, students need to analyse and check all information given in puzzles to create an appropriate solution [3]. Including puzzle tasks in the teaching, alongside routine problems, can encourage students to participate in classroom discussions [2].

Considering the usefulness of problem-posing and puzzle tasks in improving the quality of teaching and learning of mathematics and lack of research into how problem posing and puzzle tasks have been perceived by engineering students in university mathematical courses, this study seeks to explore undergraduate engineering students’ attitudes towards engaging in problem-posing and puzzle tasks. The research question sought to answer in this paper is: *what attitudes do undergraduate engineering students have towards engaging in mathematical problem-posing and puzzle tasks?*

3 METHODOLOGY

In this study, we reported two research studies that have been completed separately. In both of these studies, an explanatory mixed-method approach was designed. In the first study, 135 undergraduate engineering students participated in a problem-posing test and completed a questionnaire about their attitudes towards engaging in problem-posing tasks. Students’ problem-posing competencies were explored using eight problem-posing tasks based on Christou et al.’s taxonomy [8] related to the fundamental theorem of calculus and integral-area relationships. Furthermore,

students' attitudes towards problem posing were examined using an attitude questionnaire which consisted of twelve items on a 5-point Likert-style scale and two open-ended questions. Then, using purposeful sampling, nine students with different levels of competency and attitude were invited to participate in semi-structured interviews.

Similarly, in the second study, 135 undergraduate engineering students participated in solving four puzzle tasks (one sophism, one paradox, and two puzzles) about first-order differential equations in self-selected groups of two or three students. Then, students' attitude towards engaging in sophism, paradox, and puzzle were explored separately using a questionnaire which included sixteen Likert-style items and three open-ended questions. Finally, to explore further students' attitudes towards puzzle tasks, thirteen students were invited to semi-structured interviews.

Two senior lecturers in mathematics education examined the validity of both questionnaires. The reliability of the questionnaire was explored using Cronbach's alpha. The questionnaire items had good internal consistency; Cronbach's alpha was .89, .92, .90, and .87 for problem posing, sophisms, paradoxes, and puzzles, respectively. Students' responses to the open-ended questions and the interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. Before presenting the findings, we need to highlight that the items in the attitude questionnaires were different. In the Figures presented in the results section, PPT refers to the items of the problem-posing attitude questionnaire, and PzBL relates to the items of the PzBL attitude questionnaire.

4 RESULTS

In the following, we first present the results of some of the questionnaire items, and then the findings related to the open-ended items and interview data are presented.

4.1 The questionnaires' findings

Students' responses to the first two questionnaire items (Figure 1 and 2) showed that over fifty percent of students agreed or strongly agreed that problem posing and puzzle tasks (sophism, paradox and puzzle) are enjoyable activities. In particular, regarding Item 1, students' responses showed that 51.8% of students agreed or strongly agreed that problem-posing activities are enjoyable, and 55.9% of the students enjoyed solving sophism problems. A higher percentage of students (63.4% and 76.1%) believed solving paradoxes and puzzles are enjoyable activities to learn mathematics (Figure 1).

For Item 2, around 55% of students found the challenges of problem posing appealing. Regarding the puzzle tasks, approximately the same percentage of students believed they could learn mathematics in an entertaining way by solving sophism (56%) and paradox (60%) tasks. However, a higher percentage (77.6%) was found for puzzle tasks (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Students' responses to Item 1 of the questionnaires

Fig. 2. Students' responses to Item 2 of the questionnaires

For Item 3, students' responses showed that over 70% of students were interested in developing their mathematical skills using problem posing, and over 58% of students concurred that solving puzzle tasks can make them motivated to learn mathematics. In more detail, 73.1% of students agreed or strongly agreed that they would like to develop their mathematical skills using problem posing. Regarding puzzle tasks, 58.2% and 66.4% of students believed that solving sophisms and paradoxes increase their motivation to learn mathematics, and a much higher percentage of students (76.1%) agreed or strongly agreed that solving puzzles can motivate them to learn mathematics (Figure 3).

Students' responses to Item 4 of the questionnaires indicated that over 60 percent of students agreed or strongly agreed that engaging with problem-posing and puzzle (sophism, paradox, and puzzle) tasks could help them improve their problem-solving skills. The highest percentage was for puzzle (83.6%) and then paradox (71.6%). The percentage for sophism (67.2%) and problem posing (64.2%) were closer to each other (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Students' responses to Item 3 of the questionnaires

Figure 4. Students' responses to Item 4 of the questionnaires

4.2 Findings of the open-ended questions and the interviews

Eight main themes were identified during the analysis of qualitative data. Of these, six were found for both types of tasks, and two were only identified for puzzle tasks (i.e., *helping students develop thinking skills* and *improving mathematical modelling skills*).

Enjoyable activity: One of the themes identified in students' responses is that students found problem-posing and puzzle tasks enjoyable activities. For example, one of the students highlighted: "problem-posing activities are very enjoyable for me because they can challenge my mind and broaden my vision when solving other mathematics problems".

Improve mathematical problem-solving skills: Some of the students' responses showed that they believed engaging in problem-posing and puzzle tasks can improve their mathematical problem-solving skills. For instance, one of the students mentioned: "By engaging in puzzle tasks, students learn useful strategies that can be used to solve mathematical problems. As a result, students become good problem solvers".

Increase awareness about applications of mathematics in the real world: Some of the students believed that engaging in problem-posing activities help them to improve their awareness of applications of mathematics in the real world and its relationship with other disciplines. Additionally, many students mentioned that solving puzzles related to their major can help them increase their awareness of applications of mathematics in solving real-world problems: “By solving puzzles, students become more competent in solving real-world problems that they may encounter in the future. Unfortunately, most of the students only deal with routine problems in their university study”.

Improve students’ mathematical understanding: The majority of students believed that engaging in problem-posing and puzzle tasks can improve students’ mathematical understanding. A sample response was: “Solving puzzle leads to a better understanding of the topic, and more sustainable learning can happen when you find the correct answer after a lot of effort and consider it from different angles”.

Helping students develop thinking skills: The majority of the students believed that puzzle tasks could improve students’ mathematical thinking skills (e.g., creative, critical, and lateral thinking). Students’ responses showed that they believed solving sophisms and paradoxes can be more effective in improving critical thinking, as they need to analyse all the reasoning(s) provided in the tasks. Moreover, they mentioned that to find suitable solutions for solving puzzles, students need to be creative and look at the given task from different aspects. A sample response was: “students should critically analyse the tasks [sophism and paradox] and analyse all the reasonings used in it. However, solving puzzles needs more creativity, and students should apply their knowledge and connect them to reach an appropriate solution”.

Improve mathematical modelling skills: Many students believed that puzzles could improve students’ competency in solving mathematical modelling problems, which help them prepare for their future careers. For instance, one student said: “Puzzles are closer to reality and prepare students to solve such problems in their future work environment. Particularly in engineering, we usually need to find a model”.

Improve classroom communication: A few students pointed that communication between students and lecturers can be improved in classroom discussion using problem-posing and puzzle activities. One of the students highlighted: “some students do not like to engage in classroom discussion because mostly lecturers choose the traditional way to teach and that makes some students not like to contribute in the class activities very much; but when engaging in problem-posing activities, students can tell their opinions in the classroom”.

Improve the quality of teaching: Some students believed that problem-posing and puzzle tasks could improve the quality of university teaching. For example, one of the students expressed that “I believe posing a problem can help lecturers explain the subjects more widely and try to make a connection between different fields; therefore, it can improve the quality of teaching in the class”.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study findings indicate that many students had positive attitudes toward problem posing and puzzle tasks. In detail, the findings showed that over 50 percent of the engineering students who participated in our study found these tasks enjoyable. Among these tasks, students enjoyed solving puzzles more than sophism, paradox and problem-posing tasks. This is probably because puzzles are similar to real-world problems and students found them more relevant to the problems they may encounter in their future careers [10].

Students also perceived that engaging in problem-posing and puzzle tasks can help them to improve their mathematical understanding in calculus and differential equations courses. Moreover, many students also believed problem-posing and puzzle tasks could improve their problem-solving skills. These could be because these tasks are not routine and encourage students to inquiry into mathematics and engage them in higher-order thinking [3], such as thinking about the relationships between the mathematical concepts that they know and develop new connections between them [10].

Furthermore, many students believed puzzle tasks could improve their modelling and thinking skills in engineering mathematical courses. In detail, puzzles were perceived as more effective in developing creative and lateral thinking, while sophisms and paradoxes were perceived as more useful for improving students' critical thinking. This could be because when solving sophisms and paradoxes, one needs to analyse and criticise all the arguments in these tasks to be able to verify or refute them; while when solving puzzles, students should make a connection between all information given in the puzzles and look at it from different angles to create a solution for the puzzle which as stated above is a non-routine task [3]. To conclude, the results shared in this paper suggest that problem-posing and puzzle tasks can be included more often in engineering mathematical courses to motivate students to learn mathematics and provide opportunities for students to develop their conceptual understanding of mathematics.

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